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STUDENT TEACHERS' RETROSPECTIVE NARRATIVES OF TEACHING PRACTICE DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: LESSONS FOR A UNIVERSITY IN EASTERN CAPE PROVINCE, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to conduct a desktop research on experiences of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) students on Teaching Practice (TP) during COVID-19, with the aim to glean lessons for our own B.Ed programme to mitigate such challenges in future. Much attention has been paid to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on higher education, with a few studies having explored the TP experiences of student teachers. Although studies in education have examined useful teaching practices for succeeding during the COVID-19 pandemic, there has not been adequate literature on how the current cohort of student teachers affected by COVID-19 feel about their experiences. Piaget's Constructivism, Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, and Picciano's Blending with Pedagogical Purpose Model guided the study. The Semantic Scholar database was used to purposively select eight peer reviewed articles. Results revealed that most student teachers lacked confidence and failed to achieve the outcomes as per the TP objectives. The training period should be extended to acquire theoretical, pedagogical, practical and technological knowledge skills during times of disruption, failure of

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which, the system will produce half-baked graduate teachers that will compromise the quality of learning and teaching in the future.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic, microteaching, student teachers, teacher education, teacher mentoring

Introduction

The paper focuses on student teachers' teaching practice (TP, hereafter) skills and how that changed because of the COVID-19 outbreak. It does that by exploring their perceptions of TP and the changes they needed to make owing to COVID-19 pandemic. Teaching Practice is viewed as an important component in the teacher training programme. Preservice teachers are exposed to authentic or real classroom experiences as teacher trainees (Mtika, 2011 in Massari et al., 2021). TP prepares preservice teachers to be future-ready practitioners and has a huge impact on teacher quality (Massari et al., 2021; Sayir et al., 2022). Literature attests further that TP develops the teacher's initial pedagogical skills (Kauffman, 1992). However, the sudden outbreak of COVID-19 impacted negatively on every educational programme across various institution, TP inclusive. The rapid outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic forced organisations including universities to shut down as a way of containing the spread of the virus (Landa, Zhou & Marongwe, 2021; Chaturvedi, Purohit & Verma, 2021). The South African president, Cyril Ramaphosa was pushed to declare a state of emergency in March 2020 and pronounced hard lockdown restrictions that included controlling of people's movement, social distancing, and several other measures (Landa, Zhou & Marongwe, 2021). The unexpected complete shutdown of universities propelled lecturers and students to shift from contact to remote classes or use of digital platforms to teach university students (Dube, 2020; Fataar, 2020; Chaturvedi, Purohit & Verma, 2021). However, this sudden shift was a difficult one for historically disadvantaged rural institutions. This was because, some historically disadvantaged rural institutions of higher learning were not ready to transit to online learning and teaching (Fataar, 2020), unlike well-established universities (Dube, 2020).

Institutions that fall under the category of being historically disadvantaged rural universities are characterised by issues such as a lack of resources, poor infrastructure, lack of social cohesion and social justice among others (Sayed et al., 2016; Songca, Ndebele & Mbodila, 2021; Leibowitz, Ndebele & Winberg, 2016). In addition, some lecturers and students have difficulties with online teaching and

learning, online assessment and issues of library services, including e-library (Songca et al., 2021). This has had a negative impact on learning and teaching and other university business processes. Our view is that historically disadvantaged institutions battle with issues of redressing the 'negative Apartheid legacy' and provision of quality education to the current cohort of university students. Our perception is that such institutions experienced the 'blow' more than the affluent institutions when the COVID-19 pandemic erupted and brought lives to a standstill across the globe, hence the current study's focus on preservice teachers' experiences of Teaching Practice (TP) during the COVID-19 pandemic.

As alluded to earlier, migrating to online teaching and learning was abruptly done and had huge challenges for maintaining the academic standards and quality of the student experience in universities (Dube, 2020; Baughan, Carless, Moody & Stoakes, 2020). Globally, most universities including ours swiftly formulated policies pertaining to learning and teaching, assessment, among others as way of responding to the pandemic (Landa, Zhou & Marongwe, 2021; Tertiary Education Quality and Standards Agency (TEQSA, 2020). In our view, universities wanted to ensure continuity of teaching and learning so that students are not disadvantaged. Office for Students (OfS, 2020) states that it was a common trend among universities worldwide that despite the COVID-19 pandemic, students had to graduate successfully and be awarded qualifications. Hill (2021) posits that the objectives of the teacher education programme, theoretical knowledge, pedagogical skills and other practical skills gained before beginner teachers are deployed on TP were compromised. In the same vein, Massari et al. (2021) postulate that trainee teachers grappled to gain teaching skills in a real classroom environment before going on TP. The above cited authors hold a similar view that student teachers did not get an adequate foundational base needed to prepare them for TP. We agree with their sentiment because one of the researchers observed the same when we visited our student teachers on SBE for assessment purposes. Given the contextual background that lacks resources as discussed above and the complete lockdown, this current study, therefore, explores the experiences of student teachers (to be used interchangeably with the terms preservice teachers/initial teachers/beginner teachers) during their TP in the Eastern Cape province during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Statement of the Problem

COVID-19 pandemic forced teaching to be done in a different way since teaching could not be done in the conventional way either in institutions of higher learning or schools. Preservice teachers had to find a new way to be able to teach. We are curious to know how they navigated their TP during the pandemic. Student teachers are expected to do Microteaching (MT) before embarking on their TP. Microteaching offers opportunities to explore teaching strategies and develop novel teaching techniques. In our context, MT did not take place during COVID-19. Microteaching is a staged mini-TP where a preservice teacher prepares a lesson of his/her choice and teaches his/her fellow preservice teachers while being observed by peers and a lecturer who then critique the lesson by giving constructive feedback. However, during COVID-19 it was merely done theoretically. The study thus explored the changes that were made in student teachers' practices.

Argument

Our argument is that it is in the public domain that TP is a vital element in the training of preservice teachers and is mandatory for all teacher trainees (Shah, Ahmad & Raza, 2020). Normally, TP takes place after the teacher trainees have been adequately prepared and received the theoretical, pedagogical, knowledge and practical skills to go and teach in schools. Sayir, Aydin and Aydeniz (2022) submit that TP was immensely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, impacting negatively on the growth of teacher trainees. We argue that student teachers were struggling to marry theory and practice as part of their professional development even before the outbreak of the COVID-19. It is likely that the struggling increased during the pandemic since most universities were shut down as a measure to contain the spread of the virus. Darling-Hammond (2006) states that the public was dissatisfied with the teacher education programme in the past (before COVID-19) for they had perceived universities as ineffective in preparing student teachers. It is a fact that during the COVID-19 pandemic, significant changes that affected teacher education took place. Hill (2021) argues that any substantial shift lowers the quality of a program; on one hand, it decreases its effectiveness while on the other it increases misrepresentation and misunderstanding of quality information/knowledge. Our argument is that preservice teachers who were on TP during the COVID-19 pandemic have stories to tell that need to be shared for universities to draw lessons from. Hence, the study explored the student

teachers' experiences and their impact on their practicing as teacher trainees who went on TP with little or no clinical practice first at universities.

The outlook of TP at our university before the abrupt outbreak of COVID-19

To give the readers an insight into the context of the study, we explain how TP was done in our context before 2020 versus how TP was conducted in 2022. Our university is categorised as a historically disadvantaged institution, as indicated above, and it thus does not have adequate resources and in some cases, there are no resources at all. Therefore, this lack of resources influenced our teaching and learning. For instance, we used to teach 100% face-to-face using mostly the traditional methods of a talk- and – chalk, confining ourselves to a mortar and brick walled teaching space. We would teach (not facilitate) our student teachers the basic theories, pedagogies, etc., pouring knowledge onto them since we were convinced that we did not have well stocked libraries, no Information and Communication Technology (ICT) gadgets, etc. We used to prepare notes and give to our student teachers under the assumption that 'our student teachers had disadvantaged backgrounds that lacked exposure and therefore needed to be spoon-fed' for quality learning to take place.

Furthermore, we would physically group our students and demonstrate in class how to write a lesson plan then give them samples for them to model in their groups. Then we would demonstrate in the lecture room how to teach a certain topic (depending on one's specialisation) while our students observed us. As a class we would then discuss the best practices and bad practices of teaching a class. After that we would introduce microteaching, a practice we valued as an effective teacher training method, that affords beginner teachers a chance to strengthen their teaching skills. Oral and written feedback in the form of constructive criticism would be given by peers and the lecturer and or other lecturers in attendance as suggested by Amobi (2005). The microteaching element used to stand out as it was helping our preservice teachers to reflect on their own strengths and weaknesses and at the same time being evaluated by peers and the lecturer for them to improve their ways in preparation for teaching in the future. MT used to be done in smaller groups following a certain cycle (a cycle comprises teach, review, reflect, and re-teach) (Harmer, 2007).

In addition, our teacher trainees used to be given an opportunity to go to schools and observe how the experienced professional teachers were conducting their classes. They were given two weeks to do the observations and they were given a checklist they would use as a guide when observing. Finally, schools would be requested to give our student teachers some mentors to show them the best practices and good work ethics that develop them into good future professionals. However, all the above highlighted activities and methods changed because of the pandemic, hence this study.

Research Question

To what extent did the hard lockdown restrictions impact on student teachers' TP skills during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Eastern Cape province?

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by three theories. These complemented each other. Since the study basically talks about the pedagogies, methodologies, theoretical, knowledge construction, practical skills, reflection, and experiences, we therefore used Jean Piaget's Constructivism Theory. This theory views learning as knowledge that is acquired by processing, reflecting, and actively constructing knowledge in the mind (Mascolo & Fischer, 2005). The study also adopted Ley Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which is embedded in his Social Development theory. This theory states that students learn more through the help of significant or more knowledgeable others. The study went further to adopt Picciano's theory of Blending with

Pedagogical Purpose Model that shows how teachers can scaffold teaching using technology.

These three theories are all in agreement for they refer to pedagogy, i.e., how to teach in the classroom, constructivism, knowledge to build on, ZPD where a teacher or lecturer can assist the student to achieve on their own and where students need help of the teacher and blended learning. According to Piaget's theory, during the student's degree the lecturers interact with the students in a particular way and use demonstrations of the pedagogy for them to see how to teach in the classroom. The lecturers scaffold that process by going to classrooms and critiquing what is being done. They also show videos, interactions like plays, microteaching, etc., so that student teachers could see how things work to help the student understand progress towards ZPD (Ley Vygotsky). This way,

when they go to the classroom they can teach effectively. With the outbreak of COVID-19, what these theories advocate for was broken; for example, teacher interaction with students and demonstrating in a physical set up could not happen because of the social distance restriction that was in place. We believe students did not learn and benefit as much as they used to do before the pandemic. Picciano's theory of Blending with Pedagogical Purpose Model is a theory that supports the teaching of students by combining contact and remote learning, also known as Dual Mode Learning or Hybrid, when delivering lectures to students (Quezada, Talbot & Quezada-Parker, 2020). From Picciano's theory, our institution called the blending a hybrid mode that we adopted as a learning and teaching policy. Before COVID-19 erupted, very few lecturers and students were using online for learning purposes. We were using the traditional method of having contact classes throughout. When COVID-19 restrictions were in full force, it took some lecturers and students three months to migrate to online teaching and learning. In those three months, nothing was happening, as there were neither online nor face-to-face classes. This shows the complexity of the problem under investigation. So, the big question was, "So what next for these preservice teachers?" This study responds to this question.

Justification of using the three selected theories in the study

Previously, we indicated that the concept of teaching had changed because of COVID-19. For us this means Piaget's and Vygotsky's theories cannot address adequately the problem under investigation. Picciano's theory provides a resolution to the changes, showing how one can use the blended environment to continue with microteaching and TP. Things have changed and the context is different. Picciano speaks directly to the changes that are happening or happened, and technology is required. Therefore, Picciano's theory shows how technology can be used for pedagogic means.

Literature Review

Numerous calls were made by the government of South Africa for the field of education to adopt use of technologies in teaching and learning (Chisango and Marongwe, 2021). Most lecturers and students in historically disadvantaged universities were not very familiar with the use of technology (Fataar, 2021). Technology became significant between 2020 and 2022 when the globe was hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. The abrupt outbreak of the pandemic sent some shock waves to lecturers and students who tried to

navigate through eLearning platforms for students to continue studying (Marongwe & Chisango, 2022). However, for effective teaching and learning to happen through technology, it takes users who are techno skilled (Mbodila & Mbodila, 2022). It was strange to some lecturers to use technologies during the COVID-19 pandemic while to others it was a continuation of what they had been doing to enhance learning even before the pandemic (Fataar, 2021). Hence, we bring in Picciano's theory to establish the relevance of TP.

Impact of hard lock down propelled by COVID-19 on TP of preservice teachers

Literature attests that TP is crucial in the training of preservice teachers as it exposes preservice teachers to real classroom environments for the development of different skills and professionalism (Bolarfinwa, 2010). Similarly, Ögeyik (2016) and Hicks (2018) view teacher education as a means through which preservice teachers are educated to get theoretical field knowledge and practice-oriented teaching knowledge. As indicated by the authors cited above, preservice teachers need to gain the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to enhance their confidence (Wangchuk, 2019). To gain all the above knowledge and skills means student teachers need to have more time with their lecturers for them to be prepared for TP, which they did not have because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Darling-Hammond (2006) acknowledges that preservice teachers who have had time to be prepared by lecturers are more confident and successful than those who have not been prepared adequately. Flores and Gago (2020) perceive TP as a problematic area for preservice teachers that were greatly affected by COVID-19.

Sayir et al. (2022) state that preservice teachers lacked knowledge and experience due to COVID-19 since they had limited time with lecturers. Sayir et al. (2022) are concerned about the quality of such teachers in the future, and they recommend that they should be well-trained by having universities prepare extra programmes or extended time for the deficiency to be filled. By the same token, Shah (2020) states that preservice teachers' experiences and pedagogical skills are important for quality pedagogic performance. Like all the other authors cited above, Shah (2020) echoes the need for preservice teachers to receive thorough training on designing lesson plans, educational theories, and pedagogies that did not really happen because of COVID-19. The same scholars raised the issue of beginner teachers who did not have an opportunity to observe experienced teachers since hard lockdown restrictions were in full

force. The pandemic denied the preservice teachers an opportunity to demonstrate their practices and be assessed by their lecturers as what was happening before the pandemic when they were taken to a real classroom environment (Choy et al., 2014). In addition, communication and interaction with other students were limited. In our view, this prevented learners' exposure to real learning experiences.

Our reflections and analysis of the literature cited above

Although the study focuses on preservice teachers' TP experiences, literature about the phenomenon before the COVID-19 outbreak was also reviewed for comparison. For example, literature such as Bolarfinwa (2010) and Hicks (2018) is pre-pandemic while Flores and Gago (2020), Shah (2020), and Sayir et al. (2022) is from during the pandemic. The pre-pandemic literature shows how the teachers need to bring theoretical knowledge and apply it to the teaching practice. The sources emphasise how preservice teachers ought to teach effectively according to the context and the learners' needs. The literature from the pandemic years shows the need for preservice teachers to teach within the context they are in. It shows why it was important to consider Picciano's model adopted for this study of the blended environment in relation to the scaffolding learning that Vygotsky proposed. Therefore, reviewed literature established the relevance of TP and how teachers needed to apply prior knowledge to current context. In addition, it shows the problem/challenge that student teachers had to negotiate and navigate to be able to change and understand what the learners' needs were. Given that there was a hard lockdown, beginner teachers had to change their practices. A qualitative desktop research was done. Desktop research depends on secondary data, that is data that have already been published for other study purposes other than the current (Zhou & Nunes, 2016). The researchers used the Semantic Scholar Database to select eight peer reviewed articles that were used to reflect about the experiences of preservice teachers on TP during COVID-19 at a selected university in Eastern Cape (EC) province. We purposively selected the eight papers that helped us to understand what the literature is saying about preservice teachers' experiences and that we used to reflect critically on our context, namely the EC. The purpose of the selection was to assess what kind of experiences that were reported by these teachers during the time they went to teach without enough practice or many interactions with lecturers on the knowledge and skills development they had to practice. Table 1

below shows a summary of the eight peer reviewed papers that the study selected.

Table 1: Eight Peer Reviewed Papers Selected for the Study

Author(S)	Title	Journal
Sayir, M. F., Aydin, N., & Aydeniz, S. (2022).	The Impact of COVID-19 on Preservice Teachers' Teaching Practice.	International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies, 10(3), 17-24
Shah, M. A., Ahmad, S. M., & Raza, K. K. (2020).	Support and Challenges during Teaching Practicum: A Survey of B. Ed (Hons) Prospective Teachers of Public Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.	Sir Syed Journal of Education & Social Research, 3(3), 204-211. DOI: https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol3-iss3-2020(204-211)
Nasri, M. N., Husnin, H., Mahmud, S. N. D., & Halim, L. (2020).	Mitigating the COVID-19 pandemic: a snapshot from Malaysia into the coping strategies for preservice teachers' education,	Journal of Education for Teaching, 46:4, 546-553, DOI: 10.1080/02607476.2020.1802582.
Hill, J.B. (2021).	Pre-Service Teacher Experiences during COVID 19: Exploring the Uncertainties between Clinical Practice and Distance Learning.	Journal of Practical Studies in Education. DOI: 10.46809/JPSE.V2I2.18Corpus ID: 234095244
Quezada, R. L., Talbot, C., & Quezada-Parker, K. B. (2020).	From Bricks and Mortar to Remote Teaching: A Teacher Education Program's Response to COVID-19.	Journal of Education for Teaching, 46:4, 472-483, DOI: 10.1080/02607476.2020.1801330
Chaturvedi, S., Purohit, S., & Verma, M. (2021).	Effective Teaching Practices for Success During COVID 19 Pandemic: Towards Phygital Learning.	Front. Educ. 6:646557. doi: 10.3389/educ.2021.646557
An, B. G., & Zakaria, A. R. (2022).	A Scoping Review of Teacher Training During COVID-19 Pandemic.	International Education Studies, 15(2), 102-112.
Massari, N., Saad, N. S. M., Puteh-Behak, F., Ahmad, S., Abdullah, H., Harun, H., ... & Ishak, M. (2021)	21st Century Skills in Practice: Malaysian Trainee Teachers' Experience at Managing Students' Learning during the Pandemic:	Sains Insani, 6(1), 17-24. https://doi.org/10.33102/sainsinsani.vol6no1.227

Source: Semantic Scholar Database

Conclusion

The establishment of inclusion and exclusion criteria in research is a standard needed to be met when designing a high-quality research protocol (Patino & Ferreira, 2018), as well as achieving the external and internal validity of a study (Velasco, 2010). Accordingly, inclusion criteria are defined as a set of predefined features used in the identification of subjects, in this case variables covered in the articles that will be included in the study (Velasco, 2010). On the other hand, exclusion criteria entail factors or characteristics that disqualifies the recruited population for the study (Garg, 2016). This implies those parameters that make the articles ineligible for selection in this review.

For this review, the Semantic Scholar Database that we used to identify the papers gave us studies that were mostly done in Asia and had a lot of resemblances to our context. For example, there were some papers that were from developed countries where they have a lot of access to resources, whereas in our case there are limited resources. Therefore, we used that as an exclusion criterion for we wanted contexts that spoke to our context. We also came across papers from affluent universities in South Africa with different contexts from ours based on the resources that they have that we lack. We made a deliberate decision to exclude such papers since we were looking at what some scholars were saying that we could use to reflect on what was feasible in our context.

The inclusion criteria that we used for selecting the papers focused on such variables as teaching practice, preservice teachers in secondary schools, COVID-19 pandemic, importance of microteaching on preservice teachers, papers published between 2020 and 2022 for inclusion criteria. For exclusion criteria, papers on teachers teaching at junior secondary schools were not selected since that is not the focus of the current article. We selected the papers purposively because we were interested in this topic where students were affected during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly preservice teachers who were on or were supposed to be on TP.

We selected papers to identify how limited engagements between lecturers and preservice teachers during the pandemic affected their TP. The problem that we noticed in our context, and the knowledge gap that exists, is that we have worked with student teachers for more than 10 years and we were concerned that during the COVID-19 pandemic, the students did not have adequate engagements in the classroom with lecturers, yet they had to go and teach. Our concern was about what kind of quality of teaching they were

bringing out in their pedagogical practices. The knowledge gap is that we did not know how well these students were able to carry themselves within the learning and teaching environment/climate in the class; therefore, we needed to know more so that we could determine how effective the teaching and learning methods that we used during the COVID-19 pandemic were. Then we decided to select 6 papers that spoke to this area because it helped us to reflect about our own context and to understand what issues the students could be facing in our context so that we can improve the way in which we do things in our teaching, equipped with a better understanding of what the needs of the students are.

Findings and Discussion

Findings from the selected papers are presented concurrently with the discussion. The study sought to explore how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted on student teachers' TP. One of the findings that was common in all the selected papers regarding teacher trainees' TP experience during COVID-19 was that pre-service teachers were not ready to go for TP. This was because they had not mastered the theories, pedagogies, content, methodologies and the art of teaching. Hill (2021) reports that preservice teachers had not been given an opportunity to adequately master the specific knowledge and skills of teacher performance expectations. Our observations are being confirmed by this finding. During our TP, we observed that most of the preservice teachers were struggling with content, especially those who were teaching Geography. We observed that there was a knowledge gap. The beginner teachers could not answer some of the questions asked by Grade 12 learners. We witnessed scenarios where our student teachers were corrected by learners. The preservice teachers we observed were those who did their first year in 2020 and then went for TP in 2022. This is the cohort of students that were significantly affected by the pandemic.

They also had pedagogical issues. Preservice teachers struggled to use a variety of engaging methods. We saw preservice teachers reading a Geography textbook word for word without explaining anything as if it were an English lesson where learners were reading a comprehension passage. Nasri et al. (2020) confirm that preservice teachers had pedagogical issues (Quezada, Talbot, & Quezada-Parker, 2020). This comes back to the fact that preservice teachers enrolled during the pandemic did not have adequate time with the lecturers for them to grasp, observe, and demonstrate the knowledge and skills learnt. Mtika and Gate (2010) in Massari et al. (2021) argue

that pedagogical practice issues in using student centredness approaches were still a challenge to preservice teachers and the lecturers. The argument raised by Mtika et al. (2010) speaks to our context as well as our teacher education programme that needs a reconfiguration. We still have some lecturers who struggle to use engaging or participatory methods that put the students at the centre of learning. This translates into our preservice teachers copying the old traditional methods and they later use them in schools.

Another significant finding from the readings selected was that of preservice teachers lacking confidence and the knowhow. It is indicated in the literature that some preservice teachers did not know how to prepare a well-designed lesson plan, did not use learning and teaching media (which used to be called audio-visual aids), and that learning outcomes were poorly formulated. The preservice teachers who were interviewed in some of the selected papers blamed this on having little or no exposure to the practices of the game before being sent out to schools. Nasri et al. (2020) argue that because of COVID-19, preservice teachers could not be orientated and be given opportunities to practice their teaching for skills development. When we went for TP to assess preservice teachers in 2022, we also observed that some of our beginner teachers were not that creative. We could not understand why Geography preservice teachers could teach a Geography topic without any instructional media to enhance learning. The articles reviewed shed light that our preservice teachers were not taken through practically, hence they are not performing well. Therefore, sometimes if one does not trust the information or skills s/he has, their confidence levels are lowered.

The issue of poorly formulated lesson plans needs attention. We also observed that a majority of our students had only one file instead of two files suited to their two majors. Some of the preservice teachers did not even have the lesson plans. Some of them were teaching facing the chalkboard, some asking questions and answering them by themselves. Nasri et al. (2020) and Hill (2021) concur that some preservice teachers struggle to prepare lesson plans even for one subject. However, Nasri et al. (2020) indicate that for Physical Education and Health Education, some preservice teachers could only craft lesson plans for Health Education and not for Physical Education. Shah et al. (2020), Chaturvedi et al. (2021) and Nasri et al. (2020) attribute failure to design lesson plans properly for both subjects to preservice teachers' lack of exposure to practising teaching strategies caused by the COVID-19 pandemic's regulations put in place by different governments. This was also experienced in

South Africa (Landa, Zhou and Marongwe, 2021). In our view, this implies that such teachers can encounter some difficulties later in their career as professional teachers.

It also emanated from the articles we read that those preservice teachers had managerial classroom issues. The articles agree that some preservice teachers experienced disciplinary problems in class since they lacked the skills and theories they could adopt, adapt and apply to create a conducive environment that promotes positive learning and teaching. The articles also raised concerns regarding microteaching, namely that those preservice teachers were not adequately prepared because they missed microteaching (Nasri et al., 2020; An et al., 2022; Massari et al., 2021). The views raised by these authors are very much applicable to our context in the sense that prior to the outbreak of the pandemic we used to take our preservice teachers through microteaching in preparation for their TP. Since our institution does not have microteaching labs for clinical teaching, we used to look for a room and take our students there for them to practise teaching. However, because of COVID-19 we could not do that and as an under resourced institution we did not have that privilege of sending videos for our students to watch. Our students suffered a double blow, hence poor performance on TP.

Furthermore, Massari et al. (2021) found that use of ICTs to enhance learning was still a challenge to some preservice teachers despite having gadgets and data bundles. The same authors reported that some preservice teachers transitioned smoothly from contact to online learning for those who had access to technology appliances and internet connection. Our view is that such students and lecturers were not affected that much as they were used to online classes, and they had gadgets. This was very difficult for our students and ourselves as lecturers. When the Minister of Higher Education, Dr Blade Nzimande instructed all institutions to have online classes, some affluent universities did not take long to engage students online. The Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Mr Buthi Manamela made a call saying that there was no student to be left out. Fataar (2020) argues that remote learning in South Africa was for the affluent universities and not for historically disadvantaged universities. Some lecturers and students were not technologically orientated. While other universities quickly switched to online learning, our university started by procuring the laptops, then they trained lecturers and students on how to access and use the WiSeUp Blackboard, the e-learning platform our institution was subscribing to before the switch could be made. We can relate to what Massari et

al. (2021) are suggesting, namely that we should not use a one-size-fits all approach since students' ICT skills are not the same. These authors' suggestion is feasible and applicable to our context in that student teachers must be trained thoroughly on how to use ICTs and how to access different e-learning platforms for them to benefit from the online classes. This also corroborates the findings of Okoli and Olaniran (2022) whose study also suggested that universities in the South African context need to expose and train their staff and students in the use of online learning, as well as provide the needed digital facilities. Therefore, our take home is that we will advise our management to implement this suggestion of training lecturers and students according to their technological needs and knowledge base of how to use technologies for learning and teaching.

Conclusion

This desktop research reviewed the experiences of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) students on Teaching Practice (TP) during COVID-19, with the purpose to mirror lessons for our B.Ed programme to mitigate such challenges in the future. An overview of the background, argument, and outlook of teaching practice at our university before the abrupt outbreak of COVID-19 was presented. Whilst the study was guided by Piaget's Constructivism, Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, and Picciano's Blending with Pedagogical Purpose Model. Since data was generated through secondary approach, the Semantic Scholar database was used to purposively select eight peer reviewed articles, which was reviewed based on the objective of the study. Findings from the review revealed that pre-service teachers firstly, were not ready to go for TP, secondly, they had pedagogical issues; thirdly, they also lacked confidence and the knowhow; fourth and fifthly, they had issues with formulating lesson plans and classroom management challenges respectively. From these findings, the paper concludes that preservice teachers were not adequately prepared to go for TP. They had little or no time to meet physically with their lecturers, which impacted negatively on their performance. Some studies suggest that such students should have their time to complete the programme extended to cover what they missed because of COVID-19. Given our context, this is a feasible solution, because our year 2020 preservice teachers are inadequately prepared. Extending their training would ensure maintenance and upholding of standards. It is a fact that the COVID-19 pandemic had a negative impact on how preservice teachers were trained, especially in our context where we did not have resources and technological skills.

Recommendations

The studies consulted indicated that preservice teachers' interaction with their lecturers during the COVID-19 pandemic could have been maintained by using a variety of technologies to engage students and create simulation environments, post videos, and engaging online as suggested by Picciano's theory of Blending with Pedagogical Purpose. This implies continuity of student learning and preparing them adequately for their TP. The idea is good, and, in our view, it worked well in developed countries or affluent universities but not in our context because of lack of resources and skills. In our context, the university is in a rural area where connectivity is an issue, which is compounded by load shedding. We could not go to schools to observe how the teachers were teaching, but had we had videos from the internet to show what good practices are, we could have shown those examples of good practice to our students, what to do and what not to. So, our failure to get students in class or online to critique what they can do before going on Teaching Practice to develop them, meant there would be a knowledge and skills gap.

The paper found that the majority of student teachers lacked confidence and failed to achieve the outcomes as per the TP outcomes. Student teachers attributed this to failure to be grounded in the theoretical, knowledge and pedagogical skills. Furthermore, they bemoaned not having done microteaching and observations, lack of a practical classroom practice among other factors. The reviewed articles also show that preservice teachers on TP encountered a myriad of challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. The training period should be extended to acquire theoretical, pedagogical, practical and technological knowledge to ensure mastery of all the skills, failure of which the system will produce half-baked graduate teachers that will compromise the quality of learning and teaching in the future.

Our reflections versus our context

The university wants students to have some online activities and some face-to-face activities that they can engage in. Our curriculum needs to incorporate online activities. Depending on their experience, student teachers can tell us which aspects worked best for them and which ones did not work during the pandemic, which can inform our curriculum review.

Study Limitation and Future Studies

The study depended on secondary data in the form of studies done especially in Asia. Interviewing preservice teachers in Eastern Cape Province to establish their perceptions and experiences could have added value to the study. The preservice teachers' voices in Eastern Cape could have shed light and helped us understand their experiences and find ways to mitigate challenges faced. In addition, future studies could focus on post COVID-19 to find out lecturers' and students' experiences versus their experiences during the pandemic and mapping what universities can do to reduce the impact of pandemics on the teacher education programme in the future.

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